

Impact of Technological Investment and Ownership Structure on the Profitability of Commercial Banks: Evidence from Vietnam

Nguyen Minh Nhat

Faculty of Banking, Ho Chi Minh University of Banking (HUB), Ho Chi Minh City, 84, Vietnam
Email: nhatnm@hub.edu.vn; <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-5915-8605>

Abstract

Background: COVID-19 has influenced various aspects of people's lives and many industries and sectors of the economy, including banking. Commercial banks must improve operational efficiency as economies integrate, and catalyst improves banks' operational performance to increase competitiveness, market share, and sustainable growth.

Objective: The study was conducted to evaluate the benefits of technology investment in improving the profitability of commercial banks in the Vietnamese market. In addition, the study also analysed technology investment based on capital structure, classified into state-owned commercial banks and non-state-owned commercial banks, to evaluate the impact of each type of bank on improving profitability.

Methodology: The study assessed 26 Vietnamese commercial banks from 2012 to 2023 employing panel data, Ordinary Least Squares, Fixed Effects Model, Random Effects Model, and Generalised Method of Moments to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the regression results.

Result: The results show that technology investment can significantly improve banks' profitability. However, the study only found that technology investment is effective in non-state-owned banks.

Conclusion: The study confirms that technological investments significantly enhance the profitability of Vietnamese non-state-owned commercial banks, highlighting the strategic importance in the context of digital transformation.

Unique Contribution: The study's innovative approach examines the effects of technology investment and ownership structure on Vietnamese commercial banks' profitability. These contributions demonstrate the study's importance in guiding Vietnamese banks and policymakers through digital banking transformation possibilities.

Key Recommendation: The author proposed legislative proposals to improve the use of digital technology trends, which provide joint stock commercial banks in Vietnam with competitive advantages and mitigate risks in banking operations. Banks must develop suitable strategies to effectively implement technological developments in their operations and management practices.

Keywords: Technological investment; bank; profitability; efficiency; and Fintech growth.

Introduction

The banking sector is undergoing significant changes due to the shift, upgrading, and widespread application of digital technology in banking operations. Thanks to this, banks applying technology have a cost advantage over traditional banks (Naimi-Sadigh et al., 2022). Artificial intelligence (AI), nanotechnology, robotics, the Internet of Things, and cloud computing support businesses in transforming their business models and improving product quality, reducing banking management costs, expanding their customer database, and creating changes in customer needs, thereby leading to changes in all areas of business operations, increasing user experience and diversifying business revenue sources. Therefore, banks generate value through the combination of many business activities, such as finance, investment, trading, and insurance, to meet the maximum needs of customers. Banking is the field that applies information technology to connect customers with services that can be considered the fastest, and banking is also the field that creates the newest products and services compared to other industries. However, some studies show that investing in technology will reduce banks' profits (Gupta et al., 2018; Zhai et al., 2022).

The type of bank ownership is also an essential factor affecting the performance of banks. Studies have shown that state-owned banks operate less efficiently than joint-stock commercial banks. However, state-owned banks have an advantage over joint-stock commercial banks in having more stable profits during the crisis. Studies suggest that banks in Vietnam should restructure to reduce the state ownership ratio, reduce banks' dependence on the state, and be more proactive in business operations. Studies found a positive impact of technology investment in non-state-owned banks on the profit factor.

Due to the increasingly important role of technology investment in banking operations, the study goal is to assess the impact of technology investment on the profitability of banks in Vietnam. Based on the results, the author proposed recommendations for enhancing technology investment to contribute to bank profitability.

Theoretical Framework

Bank profitability

Bank profits are considered one of the core indicators to evaluate the efficiency of banks because this index clearly distinguishes the interest rates that banks earn from customers' savings deposits and the interest rates for loans (Chemingui, 2013). Business profits come from business profits, so profits also reflect the level of management efficiency in organisations. Bank profits are often represented through the value of net interest margin (NIM) because the index clearly shows the ability to earn money and generate profits of banks (Shawtari, 2018). Net interest margin is the ratio between the difference between interest revenue and interest expenses and the total assets of each bank. All studies use the NIM index to represent the profit factor. Therefore, after reviewing previous studies, the author uses the NIM coefficient to describe the profit value of commercial banks in the survey (Nejad, 2016; Chhaidar et al., 2023).

Impacting Technological Investment on Bank Profitability

Due to the emergence of technology and its practical application, fierce competition has been created among banks and has also made a shift from traditional business to digital transformation applications; most of the activities in banking have applied information technology for management and processing (Risman et al., 2021; Cevik, 2024). Banking operations have changed significantly with the emergence of information technology, customer service has improved, and many products and services have been born. The study defined financial technology (Fintech) as technological activities related to the Internet, including cloud computing, mobile Internet, lending, or payment (Al-Homaidi et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2021). Therefore, commercial banks spend on technology investment activities to create competitive

advantages, strengthen stability, and increase profits. However, converting from a traditional business model to applying technology to banking operations takes a long time and requires a significant investment in technology.

Studies have had mixed results on the impact of technology investment on banks worldwide. Technology increases bank efficiency but fails to improve the profitability of Indian banks when conducting research in 2006 - 2013. Research also gave similar results when the performance of most bank branches was significantly enhanced with the introduction of technology, especially for large-scale banks. In addition, digital finance, especially digital payments, is becoming increasingly important to banks' operations as e-commerce and financial technology are increasingly developing; digital finance can improve the growth rate of bank profits in the case of a well-controlled systemic risk ratio (Huy et al., 2024; Yaseen et al., 2023). In addition to finding a positive correlation between technology investment and operational efficiency, technology investment was higher for banks with high profits, efficient operations, or low financial leverage. Financial technology tools only positively impact financial stability in developed countries and reduce it in developing countries. Moreover, through service activities, internet banking can improve the profitability of Vietnamese banks.

On the contrary, some studies conclude that applying technology in banking activities causes specific impacts. The study has shown that the strong development of Fintech not only seriously affects the ability to accept risks and reduces banking efficiency but also creates shadow banking business and increases interest income, especially in large-scale banks (Akhanolu et al., 2020; Demir et al., 2022). However, this reaction is insignificant in state-owned banks but more sensitive in urban, rural, and foreign-invested banks. Many studies share the same opinion when the results prove that fintech activities reduce the efficiency and profitability of banks, but the impact of COVID-19 increases the profits of Vietnamese banks.

Impacting Ownership on Bank Profitability

The importance of capital structure in financial institutions, especially banks, has been emphasised in emerging economies. The study argued that state-owned banks will enjoy preferential treatment from the government, especially in emerging economies (Isayas, 2022; Horobet et al., 2021). Therefore, state-owned banks will have an advantage in information acquisition and business expansion compared to other banks. In addition, bank types are classified based on the equity ratio in the bank; specifically, if the state owns more than 20% of the equity, it is classified as a state-owned bank. The study gives a different ratio when classifying banks by ownership form; state-owned banks with more than 50% state capital are state-owned banks, and banks with less than 50% state capital are non-state-owned banks (Ullah et al., 2018). The study also found empirical results that capital structure affects the ability of banks to absorb, use, and transform financial technology in the Chinese market. In addition, the credit risk level of fintech banks is also lower when they have state capital ownership.

Research Data and Methodology

Research Data

The study utilizes secondary data from the audited financial accounts of Vietnamese commercial banks, comprising four state-owned banks and twenty-two joint-stock commercial banks. Data for macro variables are gathered annually as per the notification of the General Statistics Office of Vietnam. The study was done from 2012 to 2023.

Methodology

Pooled Regression OLS

The use of pooled regression methods in econometrics and panel data analysis can be traced back to early studies that sought to analyse datasets with cross-sectional and time-series components. The study introduced Pooled OLS as one of the simplest methods for handling panel data. The study also emphasises Pooled OLS as a foundational technique for panel data analysis. However, pooled OLS can suffer from bias when unobserved effects vary across units or over time.

Fixed Effects Model

The Fixed Effects model (FEM) is extensively used in panel data analysis to handle data with both cross-sectional and time-series dimensions. The study was among the first to formalize the fixed effects approach, emphasising that FEM controls for unobserved heterogeneity that would otherwise lead to biased estimates if ignored. The study points out that while the Pooled OLS model assumes that there are no individual-specific or time-specific effects, the FE model allows for unit-specific factors, making it more appropriate in most empirical settings (Boufounou et al., 2022; Huy et al., 2024).

Random Effects Model

The Random Effects model (REM) is one of the primary methods used in panel data analysis to address unobserved heterogeneity. The study notes that individual-specific effects in REM are treated as random variables drawn from a standard distribution. This makes RE appropriate when differences between units are due to random variation rather than fixed, unit-specific factors (Yang & Masron, 2023).

Hausman test

The Hausman test is a commonly employed specification test in econometrics, specifically for deciding between a Fixed Effects Model (FEM) and a Random Effects Model (REM) in panel data analysis. The Hausman test evaluates the correlation between individual-specific effects (unobserved heterogeneity) and independent variables; if such correlation exists, the Random Effects model yields skewed and inconsistent results, rendering the Fixed Effects model the more suitable option.

Feasible Generalized Least Squares

The study is credited with developing the Generalized Least Squares (GLS) estimator, which is the basis of FGLS. Aitken's theorem shows that GLS provides more efficient estimates than OLS when the error terms are not homoskedastic. Feasible Generalised Least Squares (FGLS) is commonly used to correct for cross-sectional heteroskedasticity or within-panel autocorrelation in panel data. However, the FGLS model cannot overcome the endogeneity phenomenon in panel data (Chhaidar et al., 2023).

System Generalised Methods of Moment (GMM)

The System Generalised Method of Moments (SGMM) estimate is developed to tackle endogenous variables in the model. The SGMM technique addresses unobserved endogeneity and mitigates heterogeneity issues inside the model. The Hansen test, often known as the Hansen J-test, is employed to assess the validity of instruments in SGMM (Akhanolu et al., 2020; Demir et al., 2022). The null hypothesis posits that the instruments are valid and uncorrelated with the error term. A high p-value signifies the validity of the instruments. The AR(1) and AR(2) tests are employed to assess serial correlation in the error terms of the differenced equation. In SGMM, AR(1) autocorrelation is anticipated, whereas second-order autocorrelation (AR(2)) should be absent. The rejection of the null hypothesis in the AR(2) test indicates that the instruments lack validity. Moreover, reducing the number of instruments by condensing the instrument matrix or utilising fewer lags is essential, as an excessive number of instruments might diminish the efficacy of diagnostic tests and result in biased estimates (Yaseen et al., 2023).

Research models

After reviewing the research and based on the research (Isayas, 2022; Horobet et al., 2021; Ullah et al., 2018), the research model is built on the following variables:

$$NIM_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1TECH_{it} + \beta_2SIZE_{it} + \beta_3CIR_{it} + \beta_4DEP_{it} + \beta_5LOAN_{it} + \beta_6LLP_{it} + \beta_7GDP_{it} + \beta_8INF_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$NIM_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1TECH_{it} + \beta_2SIZE_{it} + \beta_3CIR_{it} + \beta_4DEP_{it} + \beta_5LOAN_{it} + \beta_6LLP_{it} + \beta_7STATE_{it} + \beta_8TECH * STATE_{it} + \beta_9GDP_{it} + \beta_{10}INF_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

$$NIM_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1TECH_{it} + \beta_2SIZE_{it} + \beta_3CIR_{it} + \beta_4DEP_{it} + \beta_5LOAN_{it} + \beta_6LLP_{it} + \beta_7NONSTATE_{it} + \beta_8TECH * NONSTATE_{it} + \beta_9GDP_{it} + \beta_{10}INF_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

The technology investment variable (TECH) is measured by the logarithm of technology investment. Bank size ($SIZE_{it}$) is calculated by the log of total assets. Cost-to-income ratio (CIR_{it}) is measured by the income-cost ratio to Vietnamese commercial banks' total income. Deposit ratio (DEP_{it}) is calculated by dividing customer deposits by total assets. $LOAN_{it}$ is the symbol for customer loan ratio, calculated by dividing total customer loans by total assets. The study also considers two macroeconomic variables, GDP and INF.

The bank classification of this study is based on the study, which means that commercial banks in Vietnam with more than 50% state-owned capital are classified as state-owned banks; the rest are non-state-owned banks. State-owned banks have a value = 1, and non-state-owned banks have a value = 0.

Study Results

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of variables

Variables	Obs	Mean	S.D	Min	Max
NIM	269	0.0339	0.0129	0.0156	0.0941
TECH	269	4.9853	0.6329	3.1694	6.4438
SIZE	269	19.0967	1.2113	16.502	21.5566
CIR	269	0.4928	0.1392	0.1408	0.8915
DEP	269	0.6939	0.1024	0.4141	0.9095
LOAN	269	0.6069	0.1040	0.1011	0.7881
LLP	269	0.0816	0.0426	0.0042	0.2384
GDP	269	0.0597	0.0173	0.0256	0.0802
INF	269	0.0354	0.0197	0.0063	0.0909

Source: Compiled by the author

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables in the research model. The NIM exhibits a maximum value of 9.41%, a minimum value of 1.56%, an average value of 3.39%, and a standard deviation of 0.0129. The technological investment level of commercial banks in Vietnam is substantial, with a maximum value of 6.4438 and a minimum of 3.1694. The sizes of Vietnamese commercial banks vary, with the most significant value at 21.5566 and the smallest at 16.502, resulting in a standard deviation of 1.2113. The additional control variables, cost-to-income ratio (CIR), deposit-to-customer ratio (DEP), loan-to-total asset ratio (LOAN), and loan loss provision (LLP) exhibit mean values of 0.4928, 0.6939, 0.6069, and 0.0816, respectively. Vietnam's economic growth rate (GDP) ranges from

a maximum of 8.02% to a minimum of 256%. The inflation rate (INF) ranges from 9.09% to a minimum of 0.63%.

Table 2: Correlation coefficients of variables

	NIM	TECH	SIZE	CIR	LLP	LOAN	DEP	INF	GDP
NIM	1.0000								
TECH	0.2329	1.0000							
SIZE	0.0722	0.7807	1.0000						
CIR	-0.5144	-0.3961	-0.4389	1.0000					
LLP	-0.4005	0.0154	0.1703	0.1806	1.0000				
LOAN	0.1250	0.2165	0.3538	-0.3368	0.4045	1.0000			
DEP	0.4865	-0.2397	-0.3787	-0.2537	-0.3433	-0.0354	1.0000		
INF	-0.0562	-0.0842	-0.0841	0.1545	0.0517	-0.0604	-0.0385	1.0000	
GDP	0.0847	-0.0769	-0.1921	0.1189	-0.1212	-0.2255	0.1382	-0.0266	1.0000

Source: Compiled by the author

Table 2 presents the correlation matrix coefficients among the variables in the study. The likelihood of multicollinearity among independent variables increases as the correlation coefficient exceeds 0.8, resulting in imprecise regression coefficients and compromised research outcomes (Nejad, 2016; Chhaidar et al., 2023). The statistical findings indicate that the absolute values of the correlation coefficients among the variables do not surpass 0.8, thereby confirming the absence of multicollinearity within the model. CIR, LLP, and INF correlate negatively with the dependent variable NIM, while the other independent variables demonstrate a positive association with NIM.

Table 3: Regression results

Variables	POOLED-OLS			FEM MODELS			REM MODELS		
	NIM (1)	NIM (2)	NIM (3)	NIM (1)	NIM (2)	NIM (3)	NIM (1)	NIM (2)	NIM (3)
TECH	0.0060**	0.0067**	0.0055***	0.0046**	0.0046**	-0.0006	0.0048**	0.0049**	0.0034**
SIZE	-0.0017*	-0.0009	-0.0009	-0.0027*	-0.0027**	-0.0030**	-0.0026**	-0.0024**	-0.0023**
CIR	-0.0275**	-0.0314**	-0.0310***	-0.0330**	-0.0331**	-0.0336**	-0.0326**	-0.0324**	-0.0324**
DEP	-0.0337**	-0.0261**	-0.0281***	-0.0220**	-0.0220**	-0.0201**	-0.2233**	-0.0216**	-0.0203**
LOAN	0.0192***	0.0225***	0.0216***	0.0317***	0.0318***	0.0306***	0.0306***	0.0304***	0.0303***
LLP	0.0990***	0.0934***	0.0801***	0.0940***	0.0938***	0.0893***	0.0934***	0.0936***	0.0918***
STATE		-0.0091			0.0016			-0.0010	
STATETECH		0.00006			-0.00004			-0.0005	
NONSTATE			-0.0043*			0.0218			0.0004**
NONSTATETECH			0.0025***			0.0732***			0.0297*
GDP	0.0292	0.0391	0.0433	0.0264	0.0265	0.0294*	0.0272	0.0275	0.0297*
INF	0.0462	0.0754**	0.0750**	0.0535***	0.0531***	0.0482**	0.0541***	0.0571***	0.0584***

CONSTANT	0.0497***	0.0269*	0.0259*	0.0643***	0.0644***	0.0645***	0.0607***	0.0571***	0.0520***
R-squared	50.03%	54.44%	55.23%	62.77%	62.79%	64.55%	62.75%	62.68%	63.56%
Mean VIF	1.90								
F-test	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000						
Hausman test				0.9957	0.9902	0.3692			
Breush - Pagan test	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000					
Wooldridge test	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000					

*Note: *, **, *** represent statistical significance level at 10%, 5%, and 1%, respectively.*

Source: Compiled by the author

Table 3 shows the panel data regression results of three models: Pooled-OLS, FEM, REM, and model selection tests. The study was conducted with 269 observations and assessed the impact of technology investment factors on the profitability of Vietnamese commercial banks according to the capital structure of the banks.

The average VIF value is 1.90, lower than the threshold of 10, which means no multicollinearity phenomenon exists among the remaining variables in the model. The R-squared values of the Pooled-OLS, FEM, and REM models are all above 50%, so the model can explain more than 50% of the changes occurring in the NIM variable, and the regression results show consistency in all 3 models.

The regression results in all three models, Pooled-OLS, FEM, and REM, show that technology investment has a positive impact on the profitability of Vietnamese commercial banks at the 1% significance level. The independent variables SIZE, CIR, and DEP negatively impact NIM value in all models at the 1% significance level, while LOAN AND LLP positively correlate with NIM. The results do not find a relationship between economic growth rate and bank profitability, while inflation positively impacts commercial banks' profitability (Risman et al., 2021; Cevik, 2024).

The study also evaluates the impact of technology investment on profitability in state-owned and non-state-owned banks. The results only find that technology investment activities improve profitability for the group of banks without state capital in all three regression models.

An F-test was used to select the appropriate model for the study; the F-test result showed that $\text{Prob} > F = 0.0000$, less than the threshold of 0.05. Therefore, the FEM model was preferred over the Pooled-OLS model. Next, to choose between the FEM and REM models, the Hausman test was performed. The Hausman test results were 0.9957, 0.9902, and 0.3692, respectively, more significant than 0.05. Therefore, the REM model was selected as the most suitable for all 3 research models. The Breush-Pagan and Wooldridge tests were conducted to test the multicollinearity and autocorrelation of the REM model in all research models. The test results show that all 3 research models have multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity because the Prob value $> F = 0.0000$ in both tests (lower than the threshold of 0.05). Therefore, the FGLS method is developed to solve the autocorrelation and multicollinearity of the research models.

Table 4: FGLS regression results

Variables	NIM (1)	NIM (2)	NIM (3)
TECH	0.0060***	0.0067***	0.0003
SIZE	-0.0017*	-0.0009	0.0015**
CIR	-0.0275***	-0.0314***	-0.0244***
DEP	-0.0337***	-0.0261***	-0.0166***
LOAN	0.0192***	0.0225***	0.0156***
LLP	0.0990***	0.0934***	0.0706***
STATE		-0.0091	
STATETECH		0.00006	
NONSTATE			-0.0010
NONSTATETECH			0.0017***
GDP	0.0292	0.0391	0.0099
INF	0.0462	0.0754***	0.0639***
CONSTANT	0.0497***	0.0269*	0.0028

Source: Compiled by the author

The panel data regression results of the FGLS model are similar to those of the REM model. However, the endogenous variable phenomenon still exists in the panel data regression model, distorting the model's parameters. FGLS cannot solve the endogenous variable phenomenon occurring in the model, so the GMM regression method is used through instrumental variables to solve the endogenous variable phenomenon (Al-Homaidi et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2021; Yaseen et al., 2023).

Table 5: GMM regression results

Variables	NIM (1)	NIM (2)	NIM (3)
TECH	0.0083***	0.0094***	0.0067***
SIZE	-0.0033***	-0.0017*	-0.0025**
CIR	-0.0327***	-0.0230***	-0.0345***
DEP	-0.0327***	-0.0174***	-0.0212**
LOAN	0.0199***	0.0144***	0.0139**
LLP	0.0759***	0.1547***	0.0920**
STATE		-0.0095	
STATETECH		0.0002	
NONSTATE			-0.0008
NONSTATETECH			0.0017**
GDP	0.0033	0.0099	0.0159**
INF	0.0781***	0.0611*	0.0617*
CONSTANT	0.0727***	0.0208	0.0539**
AR(2)	0.787	0.969	0.793
Hansen test	0.224	0.768	0.656
Number of groups	24	24	24
Number of instrument	22	20	21

Source: Compiled by the author

Table 5 shows that in the GMM model regression results, the number of instrumental variables in all three research models is smaller than the number of groups, consistent with the rule of thumb in the GMM method according to the study. In addition, the AR(2) values in all three research models are 0.787, 0.969, and 0.793, respectively, all greater than 0.05, meaning that the research models do not have the phenomenon of second-order autocorrelation. Hansen test results in P values of 0.224, 0.768, and 0.793, respectively, meaning that the instrumental variable suits the research models. In summary, the GMM regression model can solve the existing problems in the research model and produce highly accurate results (Risman et al., 2021; Cevik, 2024; Naimi-Sadigh et al., 2022).

Discussion of Findings

The results show that technological investments can potentially revolutionize the banking industry, particularly for private and joint-stock banks. Nevertheless, governance reforms are necessary for state-owned banks to improve operational efficiency and competitiveness, given the difficulties they encounter below:

Research supports this view and argues that small banks operate more efficiently than large banks, so bank profits decrease as banks continue to increase their asset size. In addition, when researching the Vietnamese banking market, the study found that the bank size factor has an inverse relationship with bank profits (Risman et al., 2021). Operating costs (CIR) reduce bank profits at a 1% significance level; the research results coincide with the research, meaning that the more efficiently the bank operates, the lower the operating costs and the higher the bank profits. Customer deposits (DEP) reduce bank profits, meaning that Vietnamese commercial banks have not used customer deposits effectively to generate profits (Wang et al., 2021; Yaseen et al., 2023). However, the study found that lending activities increase banks' profits in state-owned and non-state-owned banks. Therefore, banks can consider expanding the lending ratio to use customer deposits effectively, but banks should pay attention to credit quality. LLP has a positive relationship with the NIM variable in the research results; NIM represents the provision for loan loss provisions, meaning that banks must generate enough net interest and non-interest margin.

For macro variables, inflation (INF) positively impacts bank profits, and the research results are similar to those of the studies (Cevik, 2024; Naimi-Sadigh et al., 2022). The study explains this phenomenon as banks follow the inflation wave and include a higher inflation premium in lending rates than in deposit rates. However, inflation increases bank profits, which is an unstable relationship, mainly when banks compete. The author does not find a relationship between GDP and bank profits; they have the same opinion. The following proposals aim to enhance the profitability of commercial banks in Vietnam by modifying capital structure, technological investment, and associated independent variables below.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The regression results of the model show that the technology investment factor has an impact on increasing the profits of Vietnamese commercial banks from 2012 to 2023 at a significance level of 1%. The research results are similar to those of the studies. Investment in technology is a trend, and Vietnamese banks are applying digital technology to their operations. Banking is also the industry that applies technology to its operations most strongly. Investing in technology will help banks enhance their reputation and attract customers by improving and developing various products and services, enhancing their competitiveness, and reducing operating costs. Therefore, bank profits also significantly improve thanks to investment in technology. Specifically, the study only found a positive impact of technology investment in non-state-owned commercial banks. The research results were supported, but they did not see the benefits of technology investment on profits in state-owned banks. This means that the higher the ratio of private and foreign capital ownership, the more effective technology investment activities are and the higher the profits of Vietnamese commercial banks. This is because joint stock commercial banks tend to compete to improve their service quality, so technology investment activities are focused on by joint stock commercial banks.

(1) The research findings indicate that the capital structure, defined by the equity-to-total capital ratio, positively influences bank performance, encompassing return on equity and total assets. Consequently, banks ought to sustain a prudent capital structure by issuing additional

shares, augmenting capital contributions from strategic shareholders, or actively retaining profits to enhance the equity-to-total capital ratio, thereby facilitating profit growth.

(2) The capital structure positively influences the return on equity and return on total assets; therefore, joint stock commercial banks in Vietnam should sustain a prudent capital structure, increasing the equity-to-total capital ratio to enhance operational efficiency. Regulatory agencies are contemplating formulating and disseminating guidelines for the comprehensive analysis and assessment of banking business models to improve the banking supervision and management framework in alignment with Basel principles. Vietnamese commercial banks have made significant progress in adopting international capital, liquidity, and leverage standards and establishing internal control systems.

(3) The research findings indicate that bank size positively influences operating efficiency, particularly the return on equity and total assets. Consequently, banks should expand their size to capitalize on economies of scale. Expanding asset size enables banks to diversify their financial operations, providing various products and services and acquiring numerous competitive advantages. Nevertheless, the expansion of asset size should derive from an augmentation of equity, thereby constraining debt. Moreover, as banks expand, they must focus on cultivating human resources with appropriate quantity and qualifications, possessing strong risk management capabilities. Concurrently, the board of directors must exhibit effective management and administrative skills to oversee human resources adequately, thereby mitigating human-related risks.

(4) An increase in the loan ratio indicates an enhancement in the profitability of commercial banks. A primary revenue stream for banks is lending, and the augmentation of outstanding loans is deemed essential for assessing a bank's operational effectiveness. Consequently, banks must determine efficiency, distribute the equity ratio aligned with financial leverage and capital safety levels, minimize capital wastage, and utilize alternative, lower-cost sources while maintaining operational safety in lending. Financial institutions should plan ahead for integrating digital technologies like blockchain, mobile banking, and artificial intelligence to improve customer productivity and service. Furthermore, to encourage innovation and competitive efficiency, officials should reevaluate governance frameworks or consider lowering the state's holding in banks. When it comes down to it, digital technologies finally allow banks to cut costs, automate mundane jobs, and simplify operations.

(5) The deposit ratio adversely affects the profitability of commercial banks. Reducing the deposit ratio is essential to enhance bank performance since an increase in the deposit ratio elevates the agency's cost of external capital, resulting in diminished earnings. Nonetheless, credit remains the principal revenue source for most joint-stock commercial banks in Vietnam; therefore, banks must enhance capital mobilization to secure financing for credit operations. Altering the business model to improve income from non-credit activities and broaden service offerings to diversify revenue streams will diminish reliance on credit operations, thereby alleviating the strain on bank capital mobilization.

(6) The data unequivocally demonstrate the unfavorable correlation with banking performance. To enhance banking performance and mitigate risks, banks can refine macroeconomic forecasts,

mentally prepare for unforeseen fluctuations in financial and monetary markets that may significantly impact banking operations, implement transparent information management, and prevent false rumours that could damage the banks' reputation and lead to a crisis of public confidence. Effectively manage late debt risks while establishing appropriate debt ratio criteria for each customer category, preventing any single group's debt ratio from overshadowing others, thus maintaining an equitable distribution of bank capital and avoiding concentration in particular market sectors.

(7) To streamline technology integration into banking operations, policymakers in other Asian nations should consider privatising some banks or reducing the amount of state ownership in these institutions. On the other hand, to get the most out of their technology investments, Asian banks need to customise them to fit local operational models and the needs of their customers.

Limitations and future research: This research only looked at the banking industry in Vietnam; its results might not apply to other nations or areas with different banking systems, regulatory frameworks, or degrees of technology usage. In addition, the study stops short of exploring the complexities of ownership, such as the impact of private equity or foreign investment on non-state-owned banks, instead focusing on categorizing banks as either state-owned or non-state-owned. The effect of ownership arrangements and technical investments on profitability in various legal and economic situations could be better understood if future research broadened its focus to encompass more than one Asian country. Lastly, future studies might zero in on particular techs like AI, blockchain, or mobile banking to see which advancements affect the profitability of commercial banks.

References

- Akhanolu, I. A., Ehimare, O. A., Mathias, C. M., Deborah, K. T., & Yvonne, O. K. (2020). The impact of credit risk management and macroeconomic variables on bank performance in Nigeria. *WSEAS Transactions on Business and Economics*, 17(1), 956–965. <https://doi.org/10.37394/23207.2020.17.94>.
- Al-Homaidi, E. A., Tabash, M. I., Farhan, N. H. S., Almaqtari, F. A., & McMillan, D. (2018). Bank-specific and macro-economic determinants of profitability of Indian commercial banks: A panel data approach. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 6(1), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2018.1548072>.
- Boufounou, P., Mavroudi, M., Toudas, K., & Georgakopoulos, G. (2022). Digital transformation of the Greek banking sector in the COVID era. *Sustainability*, 14(19), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141911855>.
- Cevik, S. (2024). The dark side of the moon? Fintech and financial stability. *International Review of Economics*, 71(2), 421–433. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12232-024-00449-8>.
- Chemingui, H. (2013). Resistance, motivations, trust, and intention to use mobile financial services. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 31(7), 574–592. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJBM-12-2012-0124>.
- Chhaidar, A., Abdelhedi, M., & Abdelkafi, I. (2023). The effect of financial technology investment level on European banks' profitability. *Journal of Knowledge Economy*, 14(3), 2959–2981. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-022-00992-1>.

- Demir, A., Pesqué-Cela, V., Altunbas, Y., & Murinde, V. (2022). Fintech, financial inclusion, and income inequality: A quantile regression approach. *European Journal of Finance*, 28(1), 86–107. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1351847X.2020.1772335>.
- Gupta, S. D., Raychaudhuri, A., & Haldar, S. K. (2018). Information technology and profitability: Evidence from the Indian banking sector. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 13(5), 1070–1087. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJoEM-06-2017-0211>.
- Horobet, A., Radulescu, M., Belascu, L., & Dita, S. M. (2021). Determinants of bank profitability in CEE countries: Evidence from GMM panel data estimates. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 14(7), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm14070307>.
- Huy, N. Q., Nga, L. P., & Tam, P. T. (2024). An empirical analysis of bank capital adequacy ratio in Vietnam: A data science approach using system generalized method of moments. *Journal of Applied Data Sciences*, 5(1), 56–70. <https://doi.org/10.47738/jads.v5i1.156>.
- Isayas, Y. N. (2022). Determinants of banks' profitability: Empirical evidence from banks in Ethiopia. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 10(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2022.2031433>.
- Naimi-Sadigh, A., Asgari, T., & Rabiei, M. (2022). Digital transformation in the value chain disruption of banking services. *Journal of Knowledge Economy*, 13(2), 1212–1242. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-021-00759-0>.
- Nejad, M. (2016). Research on financial services innovations: A quantitative review and future research directions. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 34(7), 1042–1068. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2722027>.
- Risman, A., Mulyana, B., Silvatika, B., & Sulaeman, A. (2021). The effect of digital finance on financial stability. *Management Science Letters*, 11(7), 1979–1984. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2021.3.012>.
- Shawtari, F. A. M. (2018). Ownership type, bank models, and bank performance: The case of the Yemeni banking sector. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 67(8), 1271–1289. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-01-2018-0029>.
- Ullah, S., Akhtar, P., & Zaefarian, G. (2018). Dealing with endogeneity bias: The generalized method of moments (GMM) for panel data. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 71(2018), 69–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2017.11.010>.
- Wang, R., Liu, J., & Luo, H. (2021). Fintech development and bank risk-taking in China. *European Journal of Finance*, 27(4–5), 397–418. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1351847X.2020.1805782>.
- Yang, F., & Masron, T. A. (2023). Does financial inclusion moderate the effect of digital transformation on banks' performance in China?. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 11(2), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2023.2267270>.
- Yaseen, H., Atta, A. B., & Khalaf, L. (2023). Nexus between information technology investment and bank performance: The case of Jordan. *Banks and Bank Systems*, 18(1), 68–76. [http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/bbs.18\(1\).2023.06](http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/bbs.18(1).2023.06).
- Zhai, H., Yang, M., & Chan, K. C. (2022). Does digital transformation enhance a firm's performance? Evidence from China. *Technology in Society*, 68(2022), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2021.101841>.